

TVET and Socio-economic Development in Uganda: Lessons from Chinese TVET

Kidega Charles¹, Prof. Zheng Song², Haufiku Gottlieb Ndambo Djaya³

¹Zhejiang Normal University, College of Education, China

Abstract: Numerous studies have demonstrated the significant influence on Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) has on a nation's economic growth. The capacity to integrate TVET with national economic development objectives has contributed to the economic success of many nations, notably China. TVET is seen as essential in these nations for addressing domestic issues leading to sustainable development, which places greater focus on its efficient coordination. It argues that effectively integrating TVET into national development strategies can enhance productivity, reduce unemployment, and foster sustainable economic development. The study explores the key elements of the Chinese TVET system and its role in driving socio-economic development. It articulates how China's approach to TVET has contributed to its rapid economic growth, technological advancement, and poverty alleviation. Emphasizes China's strong public-private partnerships, industry collaboration, extensive curriculum development, and practical training delivery as crucial factors in the success of its TVET system. TVET in Uganda is upset by an ineffective management structure and a lack of finance, leading to a shortage of skills and a mismatch between the qualifications offered and the demands of the labor market. These factors are major contributors to the nation's low productivity and economic stagnation. It argues that by learning from the Chinese TVET system, Uganda can develop an effective and sustainable TVET framework that addresses the country's socio-economic challenges, promotes inclusive growth, and enhances youth employment opportunities. This study used interviews and the document analysis method. Taking inspiration from China's decades-long success in developing knowledge and skills through TVET, this study explores the state, structure, implementation issues, and effects of TVET on socio-economic development in Uganda and China. In summary, It underscores the importance of aligning TVET with labor market needs, fostering industry collaboration, investing in infrastructure, and ensuring policy coherence to drive sustainable development in Uganda.

Keywords: TVET, Socio-economic development, Uganda, China,

*Corresponding Author: Kidega Charles, Prof. Zheng Song, Haufiku Gottlieb Ndambo Djaya

Accepted: 23 November, 2023; **Published:** 30 November, 2023

How to cite this article: Kidega .C, Prof. Zheng .S, Haufiku G. N. D,(2023). TVET and Socio-economic Development in Uganda: Lessons from Chinese TVET. *North American Academic Research*, 6(11), 54-69. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10214473>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2023 by the authors. Author(s) is fully responsible for the text, figure, and data in this manuscript submitted for possible open-access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

The Ugandan government established Vision 2040 in 2010 as the main framework to assist with socio-economic change. The vision focuses on policy reforms that prioritize greater competitiveness and appropriate human capital development. It will be operationalized through a series of National Development Plans (NDPs). As a result, the second National Development Plan (NDP) places a high priority on developing human capital and producing skilled labor to support national development. Uganda's skilling issues will be comprehensively addressed by the government's TVET system, which it is introducing through this strategy to meet the country's objectives of higher productivity, more efficient labor markets, and technological preparedness. The TVET policy emphasizes the need for skills for employment, including lifelong learning. Instead of focusing only on knowledge acquisition, lifelong learning emphasizes how to learn and adapt. For employment in a multicultural and globalized setting, it is, therefore, necessary to strike a balance between general education, social skills, and vocational knowledge. Additionally, to support students as they move from formal, non-formal, and informal education to vocational education, TVET needs to provide a variety of pathways. Currently, the lack of practical skills needed in the economy to generate money is not addressed by TVET delivery (Ministry of Education and Sports, 2019). Instead of placing as much focus on acquiring the necessary skills and abilities required in the workplace, the current training places more attention on obtaining academic certificates. The majority of the delivery approaches are theoretical and academic, as opposed to adaptable, practical, and work-oriented. Uganda's economy grew by 6.8%, 5.6%, and 7.6% on average between 2017 and 2018 and 2019, respectively. From 2020 to 2022, it shrank to 5.8% (Bureau of Statistics Uganda, 2022). For graduates, jobs should have been generated by this economic expansion. However, even with the expansion of the economy, the rate of youth unemployment was 6.54% in 2021 and increased to 6.58% in 2022 (World Bank, 2022). The number is likely substantially higher because over 90% of young people work in the non-agricultural informal economy (UBOS, 2011), which is linked to concealed unemployment. The economic structure, which takes into account labor demand, the skills-development regime, which controls graduate quality and the transition of graduates into productive employment, and the demographic structure, which controls the supply of labor among young people, could all be factors in the persistence and growth of youth unemployment. Youth unemployment is affected by skill development through business and Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET). TVET provides young people with the opportunity to gain practical skills, attitudes, understanding, and knowledge about diverse jobs in the productive sector by studying technologies and allied sciences.

As such, graduates from TVET institutions are typically deemed to be ready made for their chosen occupation (Tukundane et al., 2015). It is in that respect that the Government of Uganda (GoU) TVET Strategic Plan 2012 - 2022 looks at TVET as a vehicle to create employable skills and competencies relevant to the labor market (Ministry of Education and Sports, 2011). TVET in Uganda takes place in technical schools, technical institutes, technical colleges and polytechnics, medical colleges, agriculture colleges, colleges of commerce, and the Non - Formal Training Framework (NFTF) under the guidance of the TVET Act 2008. The TVET Act 2008 envisages youth empowerment in professional, business, technological, technical, and foundational skills.

Aside from the National Curriculum Development Centre (NCDC), which is now promoting competency-based education and training (CBET) to shift TVET away from traditional academic teaching and towards practical skills training, other institutions have also been established to operationalize the TVET Act 2008. To aid in quality assurance, the Directorate of Industrial Training (DIT) was established to evaluate and accredit vocational training. In a similar vein, the TVET subsector's examinations and awards were streamlined, regulated, and coordinated by the establishment of the Uganda Business Technical Examination Board (UBTEB), Uganda Nursing and Midwifery Examination Board (UNMEB), and Uganda Allied Health Examinations Board (UAHEB). Considering that the TVET subsector benefits from an institutional setting that supports skill development and facilitates a seamless transfer to other occupational.

The fact that Uganda's youth unemployment rate is continuously rising should be unfathomable (MoES, 2019). TVET institutions' inherent inefficiencies, which cause rigidities in the transition to productive employment, are partially shown by the institution's incapacity to reduce youth unemployment. In fact, according to the 2013 World Bank Enterprise Survey, 14% of Ugandan businesses saw a workforce with insufficient education as a significant barrier to business (World Bank, 2013). However, it is difficult to definitively identify a single cause of inefficiencies in skills development in the absence of a comprehensive critical examination of Uganda's TVET sub-sector. In contrast to the previous year, 2021, Uganda's unemployment rate remained relatively stable in 2022, hovering around 4.28 percent. However, 2022 was the second year in a row that the unemployment rate decreased. The government created the BTVET-Skilling Uganda program as a paradigm shift to provide Ugandans with marketable and appropriate demand-driven skills about labor market needs, with backing from the World Bank and the Ministry of Education and Sports (MoES).

This paper aims to explore the challenges facing TVET education in Uganda, what Uganda can learn from China to improve TVET on socio-economic development in Uganda, and the recommendations to the authorities to have awareness of the current situation of TVET in Uganda.

Research Methodology

This article was informed by key policy documents from government institutions on TVET in Uganda. Additional information was obtained from research findings conducted on the issue by the TVET researchers based in China and other relevant countries. More data were collected from the national TVET institutions and projects in Uganda. Some data were gathered through internet searches and discussions as well as some interviews with TVET graduates and instructors. The paper also relied on informal information from the graduates of the Universities. Data searchers were focused on the key social, economic, and political challenges that have continued to affect most university graduates in the labor market, why adaptability as well retention in the Ugandan labor market has always been very problematic without any clear evidence of abetting shortly. Multiple internet searches were conducted by the use of major search engines like Google Scholar, web Science, and Scopus for additional data mining using key search terms to establish what caused the employability of graduates in the Ugandan labor market. In addition, the study investigated how Uganda learned the best from China to improve TVET on socio-economic development. This review of the Ugandan situation focused on the field of TVET. Therefore, we could center on the socio-economic situations.

Findings and Discussion

3.1 Challenges Facing TVET Education in Uganda

There has been a significant decline in economic productivity and competitiveness, which has resulted in high rates of underemployment or unemployment (Shi & Bangpan, 2022). To address the aforementioned limitations and strategically transform the current general education and technical and vocational education and training systems from a knowledge-based and theoretical system to a competency-based system, the TVET policy was developed in consultation with all pertinent stakeholders.

3.1.1 Weak Connection to the Employment Market

The needs of the labor market and the way training is delivered in TVET system are not well correlated. According to research, TVET in Uganda does not sufficiently prepare students for the kind of qualifications demanded by the workforce. A widespread lack of practical training components in courses and the private sector's minimal involvement in TVET training are indicators of the mismatch (World Bank, 2015b). As the gap between the TVET system's goal of reducing unemployment keeps growing, this divergence is a major contributing factor to the high youth unemployment rate in the nation. In the Agago district, one of the teachers interviewed at Kalongo Technical School issued a warning about teaching "for the sake of education." and stressed the need to educate people to "give them the skills they need to

contribute to their society." The informal sector is the main source of employment prospects for young people, although it is still incredibly underdeveloped. The system for developing the skills and procedures needed to support microbusinesses and provide graduates with highly marketable and adaptable skills to meet the demands of the local and international networks of commerce, production, and technology has been consistently neglected.

3.1.2 Poor administration

A well-functioning TVET system ensures a high standard of administration management through the clear establishment and implementation of financial transfers, political interventions, and rules and regulations about performances and outcomes (W. Bank, 2020). Political meddling, teacher hiring practices, and financial transparency are the main issues affecting TVET management in Uganda. Uganda is ranked 145/176 on the developing countries corruption index and has been classified as having one of the highest reports of "petty misuse of funds" by Transparency International (2016). The amount of money that the regions and sub-divisions receive from the central government is small and poorly administered. Transfers are made by the financial supplier (the central government to regional, then regional to TVET institutions) without any defined reporting or accounting framework. The TVET industry in Uganda is mismanaged, which results in resource waste because school locations are chosen without considering the needs of the nation (Jing et al., 2022). Resource waste also leads to a decrease in funding for offices, classroom supplies, and inadequate infrastructure for teaching and learning. Furthermore, the absence of openness in the hiring and assigning of teachers (after their training) is another significant problem with mismanagement in TVET administration. Most of the bias and unfairness in the process stems from nepotism and favoritism.

3.1.3 Inadequate Instruction and Training

In any educational system, the quality of training and education are delicate topics. In a 2007 paper on the quality of education in emerging nations, Vegas and Petrow contend that while educational possibilities have increased, poverty, wealth inequality, and underdevelopment have not significantly decreased possibly as a result of subpar education (Kintu, 2019). This illustrates the scenario in Uganda, where the TVET system's poor quality of instruction and training is pervasive and the curriculum is poorly developed and poorly oriented towards real-world job demands. Teachers with insufficient qualifications are one of the main causes of low-quality training and education (Haßler & Haseloff, 2022). The scarcity of professionals and the instructors' lack of direct interaction with the industry and labor market prevents them from keeping up to speed on changes in the market and from offering instruction that is relevant to the job market. These factors also contribute to the shortage of qualified teachers. Additionally, TVET educators in Uganda have less interest in obtaining any kind of accreditation because they are viewed as inferior to other professionals, and would much rather run their enterprises. In addition, the TVET system lacks the necessary training materials, sufficient instructional guides, and well-developed training curricula to provide high-quality instruction. The TVET program still mostly focuses on theory and has little practical application in the workplace. This indicates that there are not enough professionals or learning programs to contribute to the creation of an effective curriculum that will boost young people's employability, creativity, productivity, and adaptability.

Many prospective students in remote or rural areas of Uganda face difficulty in accessing TVET institutions. Inadequate transportation infrastructure and the concentration of TVET institutions in urban areas compound this problem. As a result, students living in remote areas often have limited opportunities to pursue technical education and acquire relevant skills. This creates a significant imbalance in access and opportunities between rural and urban communities.

A mismatch between skills taught and labor market demands: The mismatch between the skills taught in TVET institutions and the actual demands of the labor market is a significant challenge. This can lead to a situation where graduates are unable to find suitable employment. For example, if a TVET institution heavily emphasizes traditional artisanal skills while the job market demands digital skills, graduates may struggle to secure employment. Bridging this gap

requires regular assessment of the labor market needs and continuous updating of TVET curricula and programs.

Insufficient internship and apprenticeship opportunities: Practical training through internships and apprenticeships is crucial for TVET students to gain real-world experience and apply their skills in practical settings. However, in Uganda, there is limited availability of internships and apprenticeships for TVET students. This lack of industry exposure and hands-on experience hampers their ability to fully develop and refine their skills. Establishing partnerships with industries and providing more internship opportunities can help address this issue.

Stigma and negative perception: The perception that TVET education is inferior to academic education is a significant challenge in Uganda. This stigma often leads to low enrollment rates in TVET programs. For instance, a student interested in computer programming might choose an academic degree program instead of a technical program focused on software development, assuming it carries more prestige. This creates an imbalance in the job market, with a surplus of academically qualified individuals and a shortage of skilled technical workers.

3.1.4 Gender disparities

Given that women make up more than half of Uganda's population overall (UN Population Division, 2017), their education and skill development are essential to the country's economic diversification and employment growth. The enrollment of women in technical and engineering programs is significantly lower than that of men, indicating a serious gender imbalance in Uganda's TVET system (UN, 2015). The food, health, and service industries account for a disproportionate share of the small number of women enrolling in TVET programs. This is partly because of societal norms that restrict women to performing traditional occupations. Due to this, there is now a performance disparity between male and female entrepreneurs, with women being portrayed as having lower potential and productivity, which has a detrimental effect on the economy. In addition to the ongoing problems of sexual harassment, violence, and low social status for women, particularly in the area of entrepreneurship, women are dissuaded from pursuing education in technical disciplines. One of the key components of Uganda's structural change has been highlighted as developing greater abilities for embracing and modifying technologies (Sosale & Majgaard, 2016). Only when men and women fully participate in the process, without any kind of discrimination, will this transition be feasible? An inclusive knowledge and skills training program is essential for the transformation of the nation since women who receive education and training not only improve their own lives but also the lives of entire societies. Furthermore, Uganda's need for trained labor forces makes it imperative to do away with traditions and step-up initiatives to advance women in TVET.

3.1.5 Inadequate infrastructures

Uganda's population has increased dramatically over the past 60 years, and between 2010 and 2020, this trend is predicted to continue (National Institute of Statistics, 2013). Since over 60% of the population is under 30, there is a great demand for education, which calls for Ugandan responses in the form of infrastructure, equipment, and the distribution of material, financial, and human resources (Agole Peter, 2022). As a result, in reaction to this circumstance, technical secondary and postsecondary institutions have been built throughout the nation in recent years, marking an expansion of TVET. There were 456 technical schools in 2012, both public and private, with a 75% expected enrollment growth rate (Kom, 2012). To meet the demands of teaching and learning, the TVET industry has been urged to invest more due to the expanding number of learners. However, TVET faces a lack of basic infrastructure due to the nation's economic constraints, which has a significant impact on the delivery of education. It has been noted that many tertiary colleges lack functional laboratories, 57.2% of technical schools lack workshops, learning, and teaching resources are outdated, and 4.4% of classrooms are made up of makeshift materials (Ochola & Kavinda, 2019). The current infrastructure is undermaintained, insufficient, and non-specialized. According to the National Institute of Statistics (2010), 24% of secondary schools, including TVET institutions, did not have working computers available for students at the time of information and communication technologies. The issue of inadequate infrastructure makes it difficult for people to get

quality experience and learn the skills they need to advance. Numerous interns at Albilnino Teacher Training College and Kalongo Technical Schools who were questioned for the study bemoaned their lack of adequate practical experience, which they attributed to the institution's inadequate infrastructure.

3.2 TVET System in China

China's socio-economic development has benefited greatly from technical and vocational education and training (TVET). With over 11,300 schools and vocational institutions and over 30 million students enrolled, China currently has the largest TVET systems in the world.

To create a comprehensive system of technical, vocational, academic, and skills education and training (TVET) and to increase public awareness and recognition of the industry, the Chinese government has actively changed its policies. In January 2019, China released the National Implement Plan for TVET Reform. The Plan planned for the creation of a state-of-the-art, Chinese-specific TVET system as well as the establishment of national TVET standards. In the beginning, the Plan originally announced the implementation of a 1+X certification pilot program, encouraging students to earn both a higher vocational education diploma and occupational and competency-based certificates (X) (A. D. Bank, 2021). The national credit bank system will consider the learning hours and outcomes for the 1+X certification as academic credits. To contribute to the development of a society where learning never ends, the credit bank will promote the identification, accumulation, and transformation of diverse learning experiences and outcomes. A historic National Vocational Education Conference in 2021 sparked a few fresh initiatives to support the Plan's execution. Upgrading TVET programs and institutions from three-year diploma to four-year bachelor programs is one of the most important steps. To better match the supply of highly qualified workers with industry demand, significant collaboration, and integration of businesses, industries, and educational institutions were also encouraged. This included course design and delivery, faculty training and coaching, practicum and apprenticeship, and more. TVET, which is increasingly acknowledged as an equally significant form of education, will kick off a new five-year cycle of national strategic planning in 2021. It is a powerful engine for economic development and a catalyst for career preparation.

The Vocational and Technical Education Law of the People's Republic of China, which was passed in 1996, governs TVET in China. The policy's main goals are to: increase secondary TVET enrollment, particularly in rural areas; improve overall enrollment at TVET institutions and the quality of education; enhance and coordinate secondary and post-secondary TVET with general education; modify courses and curricula to better meet the needs of real-world employers; raise the caliber of teaching staff; and, lastly, encourage improved collaboration between businesses, employers, and TVET institutions (Shi & Bangpan, 2022). In China, the Ministry of Education (MOE) and the Ministry of Human Resources and Social Security (MOHRSS) are the primary departments overseeing vocational schools.

3.2.1 The State and Administration of TVET in China

The Junior and Senior Vocational Schools (SVS), Secondary Technical Schools (STS), School-based Vocational Education Providers (SWS), Higher Vocational Colleges (HVC), and Senior Skilled Workers Schools (SSWS) comprise the structure of the TVET system in China (Wang, 2006). While skilled workers' schools prioritize industrial careers, vocational schools offer clear thinking on crafts and commercial vocations. After three or four years of study, students receive a leaving certificate. (Shi & Bangpan, 2022) The two to three years of vocational college education at the tertiary level are designed to prepare graduate students for practice-oriented roles in production. The junior secondary technical vocational schools, which are typically found in rural areas with weaker economies, prepare students for senior secondary school enrollment and lead them to obtain a leaving certificate or a rating certificate by MOHRSS vocational criteria.

3.2.2 The Chinese TVET structure

The MOE is responsible for overseeing adult high schools, secondary vocational high schools (SVS), and secondary technical or specialized schools (STS), which make up three-quarters of the senior secondary level (Zhang et al., 2020).

The Ministry of Human Resources and Social Security oversees the skilled workers schools (SWS), which make up only 25% of all schools. (MOHRSS). The most sought-after secondary courses include computer technology, manufacturing, civil engineering, and retail and hospitality. At the post-secondary level, the Ministry of Education oversees the Higher Vocational Colleges (MOE). Higher Vocational Technology institutions and higher technology specialized schools, five-year higher vocational programs offered in general secondary specialized schools, and short-term vocational colleges with the qualities of being vocational, local, and practical make up the post-secondary TVET institutions (Pilz, 2012). Higher education in the workforce is offered in general higher education institutes and adult higher education institutes. Reformed general specialized education schools emphasize higher vocational technology talents.

3.2.3 TVET Admission

China prioritized TVET enrollment more since the nation is moving towards a knowledge-based, innovative economy that needs more skilled labor. China has the largest vocational education in the world with an enrollment of 30.88 million students and 10 million graduates per year. According to a 2013 statistics report from the Ministry of Education of the People's Republic of China, 5.4 million of the 13 million students enrolled in all upper secondary schools were in vocational education programs, and 5.5 million of the 13 million graduates from all upper secondary schools attended vocational education programs. This demonstrates the impressive growth in TVET sector enrollment in China. Furthermore, the 2009 State Council report set a goal of 3 million new students each year for higher TVET institutions, with a total enrollment of 10 million and trainees of all off-campus TVET courses attain 150 million persons (Shi, 2012).

3.2.4 Chinese TVET system driven by demand

An important part of China's extensive educational system, skill development at TVET and higher levels has a significant impact on raising national employment and competitiveness. The Chinese government has established a broad vision for a "modern" TVET system that is on the one hand run by the government but closely collaborates with the producing sector over the past two decades. It directly reacts to the shifting competency demands and educational standards in the work market (Postiglione & Tang, 2019). The "top-down" and "bottom-up" approaches combined with the expanding economy have yielded outstanding outcomes in the TVET sector. New programs that are highly relevant to local industries and have high employment/self-employment rates have been designed with industry cooperation, whereas programs that are less relevant and have lower employment rates are either closed or adjusted.

3.2.5 Training

The following are the goals of training in China's technical and vocational institutions:

- Establish links between the development of skills and a long-lasting career through chances for lifetime learning.
- Encourage students to learn through hands-on experiences in the classroom to raise their awareness of skills.
- Assist industry and educators in creating training programs and procedures that will be appropriate for the demands on skilled labor in the future.
- Provide pupils with the learning resources they require to identify and pursue a skill.
- Assist organizations and teachers in creating fresh, cutting-edge approaches to imparting in-demand skills to the next generation of workers. China is creating new, contextualized TVET training programs to make them relevant to sustainable development. According to the argument for a "total" education program, which does not limit people's learning experiences to the classroom but also to society, China's TVET training program is constantly updated and views the curriculum as a dynamic process due to societal changes (Bilbao, Purita P., 2008). The training curriculum is based on the National Competency Standards for Work, which were created with industry input and implemented by the appropriate Ministries (Bai, B. & Geng, 2014). For example, in senior secondary vocational schools, the curriculum is structured so that one-third of the courses cover general academic competencies as defined nationally by the Ministry of Education. Finally, the remaining one-third is defined again about the occupational field and is decided locally at the

school level with the assistance of local businesses. This second third of the defined content is related to the specific occupation (Santosh, Devi, & Gandhi, 2014).

3.2.6 Funding

The government is the key actor in public TVET institution's finance, whereas private institutions are funded autonomously. Chinese central government has allocated a national budget of RMB 25.71 billion yuan (about 3.68 billion U.S dollars) in 2020 (Xinhua) to boost TVET systems. Nonetheless, a wide range of partners, including the government, businesses, relevant sectors, and civil society, provide funding for post-basic education, including secondary and higher education. According to the Chinese law on vocational education, a business must pay for the training of individuals it intends to hire. As a result, steps are taken to make it possible for businesses to assist their target TVET colleges and students more. After conducting a study investigation in several Chinese vocational schools and speaking with a teacher at Yongkang Vocational School, the author discovered that many businesses visit the school in search of potential employees among the soon-to-be graduates. These businesses occasionally provide financial assistance to the students they hope to hire in the future. Furthermore, one of the instructors at Jinhua Polytechnic College claims that the college obtained learning infrastructures as a result of partnerships with businesses. For example, Jinhua Polytechnic College obtained automobiles and machinery from their partner to guarantee auto mechanics major students have hands-on experience. In China, enterprises, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), as well as other public organizations or individual citizens are strongly encouraged by the State to provide funds or scholarships to support TVET provision. Above all, all the earnings collected by TVET institutions are used for development purposes.

3.3 Impact of Chinese TVET on Socio-economic Development

3.3.1 Employment Opportunities

Chinese youngsters now have jobs thanks to the employment-driven TVET system that China has implemented, which has also greatly improved labor market outcomes. China's economy grew quickly between 1990 and 1996 (the TVET Law was implemented in 1996), and one noteworthy characteristic of this expansion was that it was correlated with a very high increase in labor productivity in the industry (Ghose, 2005), which was partially attributed to TVET's development. China's job condition greatly improved between 1990 and 2011, as the following illustrates:

The shifting nature of employment that comes along with economic expansion is significant when examining the social changes that accompany economic development (ILO, 2015). TVET provides young people in China with the opportunity to enhance their capacity for self-employment. TVET graduates are eligible to apply for government loans with subsidized interest rates to help with

(a) tax reduction and exemptions, as well as administrative charges. If the graduate satisfies certain requirements, further options such as security-backed loans and discounted interest are also available.

(b) Social insurance subsidies based on the qualifications of the candidates.

3.3.2 Poverty alleviation

One of the main concerns facing the global society in the twenty-first century is the reduction of poverty. In addition to helping people, TVET-provided employment and job creation chances have also contributed to the reduction of poverty in local communities, particularly in rural areas. In China, skill development is a means of empowering people to develop marketable technical skills and practical productive competencies. Training in technical fields like agriculture, poultry production, manufacturing, food production, and dairy products was made possible by TVET. Nearly 80% of all vocational institutes in China are situated in rural areas, as noted by Dr. Yang Jin, Head of the Central Institute for Vocational and Technical Education (CIVTE).

Particularly for young people, women, and members of ethnic minorities, these career frameworks are essential in

providing a means of escaping poverty (Janne Leino, 2017). 386 agriculture colleges in the nation offer farmers certification and training. The program combines fieldwork and classroom learning with entrepreneurship. Vocational education training in agriculture-related fields has been crucial in addressing numerous concerns about public health, reducing rural-urban migration, enhancing agricultural productivity, and boosting Chinese farmers' marketability.

3.3.3 Creativity, Innovation, and New Technology Development

The twenty-first century's technological, informational, and communication advances created a demand for new skills to meet the demands of the global modern economy. The introduction of new work practices, industrial processes, and technological advancements has intensified the demand for higher-order skills and productivity. China's TVET was created in a variety of ways to prepare students for the challenges posed by new technological development. These included technological and scientific tracks that support innovative education, modern educational technology, and the development of autonomous skills in an online learning environment. Like in other nations, technical knowledge obtained through TVET in China is combined with creative abilities and career counseling. (Yu, 2012). It enables the nation to stay up to date with the rapidly evolving technical landscape by fostering innovation in high-quality technological solutions.

For China's development projects about industrialization, urbanization, and internationalization, TVET has been crucial in supplying top-notch skilled labor (Zhang et al., 2020). Developments in the nation's information technology sector have the power to change the vast population and perhaps reorganize the Chinese economy. According to the nation's development plan, these advancements are connected to the growth of the Technical and Vocational Education program. China is now regarded as one of the world's technologically advanced nations thanks to its emphasis on TVET development.

To address the global challenge posed by climate change and carbon emissions, health, poverty, environmental degradation, and other issues, China's Hong Kong Special Administrative Region, which is well-known for its great technological capabilities, established a strategic development plan in 2014 that focused on economic development, innovation and technology industries, vocational education, and environmental protection (The Government of Hong Kong SAR, 2016). Recognizing that TVET can help create a better future by providing an abundance of highly qualified human resources, China aims to have 39 million high-skilled workers by 2020, including 10 million technicians and senior technicians who will be more multifaceted, relevant, and connected (Jiang, 2012).

3.4 Lessons from Chinese TVET Education

The Chinese government attaches great importance to TVET and the education system in order to foster a skilled workforce, drive economic development, and promote social mobility. This emphasis reflects the government's commitment to building a knowledgeable and skilled society. The government has placed significant importance on Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) as well as the education system as a whole.

As was already established, numerous studies have shown how important TVET is to economic growth. Like in many other industrialized nations, China has acknowledged the important relationship between TVET and economic expansion (Zouliatou, 2017). China has experienced several achievements in the field of science and technology thanks to the growth of TVET, which has also significantly improved the well-being of the Chinese people. Despite the applicant's establishment of a new firm. In addition, the government encourages the growth of Medium and Small-Scale Enterprises (SMEs) to create jobs: This has led to an increase in the number of independent contractors in China, who are predicted to become an increasingly influential political and economic force. However, learning from a successful system to develop creativity and innovation, based on local realities and country priorities, could be a practical solution to solve TVET challenges in Uganda. Therefore, reconstructing the TVET system in China's National Bureau of Statistics

(NBS) reports that in 2009, the proportion of self-employed workers in the country's workforce increased to 12.5%. About 5.6 million individuals worked for themselves in China's Hebei province in 2015. Many of these individuals had previously attended post-secondary, adult, informal, and other types of technical and vocational education institutions. Due to the realities of the nation and its effort to transition to a modern economy, the Chinese TVET system has many obstacles today (Jing et al., 2022).

Uganda should leverage its positive connections with China to expand educational collaboration in TVET development domains by 2030, as stated in the national development policy, and subsequently benefit more from Chinese experiences. First and foremost, given that the effectiveness and efficiency of the nation's financial management have been questioned, the Ugandan government must make sure that funds allocated for Technical and Vocational Education (TVET) are used appropriately (Reviews & Education, 2012). A sizable percentage of the pitiful amount of money allotted to TVET does not reach its intended goal, and the remaining amount is lost to corruption. Every level of governance might use China's expertise in effectively managing the funding allotted to TVET for the management of TVET finances. The second thing that has to be emphasized is the connection between TVET and industry. Businesses in China are highly encouraged to get more involved in curriculum development, which enables them to discover their interest in the TVET sector and reap program benefits such as sufficient and effective workforce employability and high labor productivity (Kinega, 2021). Such a practice might be used in Uganda to help businesses fulfill their output goals, support the nation's development goals, and enable its people to transition from poverty to prosperity. Additionally, by providing land at discounted rates for the establishment of TVET institutions, the government might incentivize businesses to actively engage in the growth of TVET (Dobbo, 2018). In situations such as these, instruction and learning are set up. The government of Uganda should provide incentives to businesses engaged in such initiatives if the country is to pursue its goal of becoming an emerging economy.

Thirdly, TVET should receive greater priority in the national education policy due to its impact on socioeconomic growth, and this may be achieved by offering incentives to students to make TVET more appealing. Lowering tuition costs generally, for example, will entice more students to participate in TVET programs, particularly the impoverished. This is similar to China's education strategy, where the government heavily subsidizes the education of students from low-income families (Warmerdam & van Dijk, 2013). As a result, this will be a workable answer to the problem of growing enrollment at Ugandan TVET colleges. Uganda needs a thorough institutional overhaul that addresses everything from managerial techniques to skills acquisition of learners and practical application of TVET skills. Many students from various TVET institutions and training centers complained about the government's attitude towards their entrepreneurship endeavors during this study process. They felt that their efforts were being ignored, which frustrated them a great deal (Nadialista Kurniawan, 2021). To prevent this and promote entrepreneurship and job creation, the government should work with businesses to offer these deserving students' scholarships or loans, as well as subsidize their projects, which would then be developed and grown with the businesses' experience. Furthermore, formal connections between educational personnel and both public and private businesses are required to allow educators to stay current with the latest developments in the field of teaching and learning.

In general, a nation's economic growth depends on the efficacy and increased productivity of its labor force, as well as on producing better results and adding greater value. Ethiopia, for example, has benefited greatly from increased values added to Technical and Vocational Education and Training through its educational cooperation with China. As a result, Ethiopia's national poverty rate has decreased significantly, falling from the highest in the world in 2000 to 29.6% in 2014 (IMF, 2011; World Bank, 2015a). Ethiopia is currently developing steadily and quickly in the direction of industrialization. Through this win-win collaboration with China, Cameroon might enhance the value of its TVET development and find answers to its social and economic issues.

3.4.1 Industry and Educational Collaboration

In China, vocational colleges and businesses work closely together. The TVET institutions are driven to build their brands and turn out employable graduates (Dobbo, 2018). Companies collaborate with vocational institutions on planning, course creation, teaching, and program evaluation, enabling students to receive hands-on training, exposure to the industry (apprenticeship), and program evaluation. While local governments offer incentives to businesses to promote this kind of cooperation, the businesses themselves believe that they have a stake in developing qualified and competent workers. In China, the competition for skilled workers can be very intense. Numerous businesses actively entrust regional TVET institutions to create certain training programs and "order" a set number of graduates with requirements. Particularly small and medium-sized businesses value the TVET teachers and students' contributions to R&D efforts to address their technological issues, thus they are eager to work together.

To satisfy the demand for a competent, "ICT-capable" workforce required by new manufacturing technologies, TVET institutions are also increasingly utilizing technology in the delivery of training (Tukundane et al., 2015). Due to the advantageous conditions brought about by China's quick industrialization and urbanization, graduates from vocational colleges can obtain employment, including self-employment, quite quickly after graduation. More than 90% of Chinese TVET graduates find meaningful employment within six months of graduation, according to the most recent MyCOS survey.

3.4.2 TVET Teacher Development

The majority of TVET instructors in China, as in many other nations, only hold academic degrees. To ensure that all TVET teachers are "double qualified" with both academic and skill qualifications, the government is now providing incentives for the teachers to obtain their own skills certifications (Jiang, 2012). Teachers in vocational schools are expected to complete a two-month practical training program in businesses for their continued professional development to advance in their careers. The hands-on training, they receive at the businesses enables students to work with the newest technology and develop the necessary skills for the changing demands of the sector. Additionally, colleges hire business professionals to teach practical courses on a part-time basis (Olema, 2018). ICT-enabled teacher adoption of student-centered pedagogy encourages students to actively participate in and take ownership of their learning experiences and encourages them to actively participate in and take responsibility for their educational experiences. At the TVET level, the unwavering emphasis on teaching and academic excellence is also evident.

3.4.3 Quality and Applicability

The Chinese TVET and skills development (common in other East Asian nations as well) integrate "education" and "training," promoting both general foundational skills and specific technical and vocational education at the secondary and tertiary levels. While many skills development systems emphasize the "training" component. There is a system of occupational standards, testing, and certification for technical and practical abilities. The development of training programs and curricula takes into account the specific needs of the labor market and is based on occupational standards (UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2011). Companies are actively involved in creating curricula and setting standards. This guarantees that vocational institutions generate qualified trainees with the requisite abilities, information, and marketable attitudes. The fact that the curriculum emphasizes practical training both in a college setting and, in the workplace, fusing work and learning, is particularly significant (Postiglione & Tang, 2019). When creating institute-specific curricula to adhere to the broad occupational criteria established by the Ministry of Human Resources and Social Security, TVET institutions have a good deal of autonomy and the academic requirements established by the Ministry of Education. To assure quality, the Ministry of Education inspects vocational institutes for compliance.

3.4.4 Communist Party System. The Chinese government under the leadership of His excellency xi Jinping has implemented policies and allocated substantial funding to enhance TVET and education (Shi & Bangpan, 2022).

National plans and policies encourage the development of high-quality TVET programs and institutions, ensuring that they receive adequate financial support. This implies that the government should also put more efforts on funding to ensure quality TVET education in Uganda. The government has worked to expand the number of TVET institutions, creating more opportunities for students to pursue vocational education. This expansion aims to meet the increasing demand for skilled workers in various sectors of China's rapidly growing economy. The government has worked to improve the curriculum and standardization of TVET programs. Reforms have been implemented to align the curriculum with the needs of industries, ensuring students acquire relevant skills and knowledge. Standardization measures aim to enhance the quality and efficiency of TVET education. The Chinese government recognizes the importance of education accessibility and strives to ensure equal opportunities for all. Efforts have been made to improve access to education in rural and economically disadvantaged areas. Scholarships and financial aid programs are also available to support students from underprivileged backgrounds. The government has invested in modernizing and upgrading the infrastructure of TVET institutions. This includes the construction of state-of-the-art workshops, laboratories, and training facilities, equipped with the latest industry-relevant technology and equipment (Zhang et al., 2020). By providing modern infrastructure, the government aims to create a conducive learning environment for TVET students. Ugandan can also borrow these ideas to work on the proper development of TVET systems in Uganda. The Chinese government actively seeks international cooperation in the field of TVET and education. Collaborative partnerships with other countries are established to exchange best practices, promote mutual learning, and enhance the global competitiveness of the Chinese education system. International exchanges and programs provide opportunities for students and educators to gain exposure to different educational systems and cultures. The government has invested in research and development in TVET and education. This includes conducting studies and surveys to identify emerging skills demands, conducting research on innovative teaching methods, and fostering the development of educational technologies. Research findings are used to shape policies and improve the effectiveness of TVET programs. Through these comprehensive efforts, the Chinese government strives to build a high-quality TVET and education system that prepares students for the demands of the labor market, supports economic growth, and contributes to national development. The focus on ensuring accessibility, relevance, and continuous improvement demonstrates the government's commitment to cultivating a skilled and educated workforce for the benefit of society as a whole.

Conclusion

Knowledge and skills are the primary drivers of modern economies, according to the human capital concept (Becker, 1994). China actively invested in Technical and Vocational Education and Training to educate young, responsible citizens who could perform well and be productive, based on Confucius's assertion that "**Memorising knowledge only, no matter how much you learn, won't educate a capable person, who could perform the tasks adequately**" (Wenjin Wang, 2010). For Uganda to address its issues with TVET growth, it would be beneficial to consult the Chinese TVET model at various points while keeping in mind the national circumstances. Therefore, the study's conclusion makes the case that if TVET is implemented effectively at all governmental levels in Uganda. Technical and Vocational Education in Uganda could undoubtedly aid the nation in overcoming its greatest challenges to increase employment opportunities, decrease poverty, and support economic development if it is well-coordinated, supported by a persuasive TVET development policy, properly links TVET to the labor market, involves employers heavily in the development of TVET curriculum content, reforms the current TVET curriculum comprehensively and effectively, and receives more funding.

Recommendations

Enhance the professional development of TVET instructors by providing them with continuous training programs that focus on industry-oriented skills and teaching methodologies. This will ensure the delivery of high-quality and up-to-date instruction. Develop relevant and updated TVET curricula that align with the needs of the labor market and industry. Seek opportunities for international cooperation and collaboration with countries that have successful TVET

systems like China. This involves integrating practical skills training with theoretical knowledge, emphasizing problem-solving and critical thinking abilities, and incorporating emerging technologies.

Create platforms for continuous dialogue and collaboration between TVET institutions and industries. Foster close collaboration between TVET institutions and industries to ensure that training programs are responsive to current and emerging industry needs. Establish partnerships, apprenticeship programs, and internships to provide students with real-world experience, improve their employability, and enhance ties between academia and industry. This could involve establishing industry advisory boards or councils, where representatives from various sectors provide input and guidance on curriculum development, industry trends, and emerging skills requirements. This ongoing engagement would help keep TVET programs relevant and up-to-date.

Invest in upgrading TVET infrastructure, including classrooms, workshops, laboratories, and equipment. This would ensure that students have access to modern and state-of-the-art facilities, providing them with hands-on learning experiences and practical skills training.

Create specialized Centers of Excellence within TVET institutions, focusing on sectors with high growth potential. These centers would provide advanced training in areas such as technology, engineering, healthcare, agriculture, and hospitality. By equipping these centers with modern facilities and highly qualified instructors, they would serve as hubs for innovation and skills development, attracting top talent and investment.

Integrate entrepreneurship education into TVET curricula. Encourage students to develop an entrepreneurial mindset, teaching them how to identify business opportunities, manage resources, and navigate the challenges of starting their enterprises. This would promote self-employment and job creation, contributing to economic growth and reducing unemployment rates.

Establish rigorous quality assurance mechanisms to ensure the standardization and effectiveness of TVET programs. This could include accreditation processes, regular evaluations, and monitoring of TVET institutions. Peer review systems and benchmarking against international standards would also be valuable to maintain quality and international recognition.

Encourage TVET institutions to engage in research and development activities to foster innovation and address industry challenges. This would contribute to knowledge creation, technological advancements, and the adaptation of new technologies and practices in the TVET sector. Explore opportunities for collaboration with Chinese TVET institutions to exchange experiences, expertise, and best practices. This could involve joint research projects, faculty exchange programs, and student exchange programs. Leveraging the experiences of successful TVET systems like China can provide valuable insights and strategies for enhancing Uganda's TVET system.

Promote inclusivity and gender equity in TVET by actively encouraging the participation of girls and vulnerable populations. Implement strategies to enhance the public perception of TVET and promote its attractiveness as a viable career pathway. This includes raising awareness of the value and potential of TVET, showcasing successful TVET graduates, and dispelling societal stereotypes about vocational education. Create support mechanisms, scholarships, and incentives to attract and retain underrepresented groups in TVET programs. This would not only contribute to the empowerment of marginalized communities but also help diversify the workforce and meet labor market demands.

Establish a culture of lifelong learning by providing opportunities for upskilling and reskilling to both TVET graduates and existing workers. Develop short-term courses, workshops, and apprenticeship programs that cater to the needs of individuals seeking to enhance their skills or transition to new careers. This would ensure the continuous relevance and adaptability of TVET graduates in a rapidly changing job market.

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Integration: Emphasize the integration of ICT in TVET curriculum and delivery. Provide access to digital tools, e-learning platforms, and online resources for both instructors and students. This would help enhance teaching and learning methods, as well as provide exposure to the digital skills required in today's technologically driven world.

By implementing these recommendations, Uganda can further enhance its TVET system, ensuring that it equips individuals with the skills and knowledge needed to succeed in their chosen career paths.

Author Contributions: On the first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Agole Peter. (2022). Confronting the challenges of University Technical Vocational Education and Training in Uganda. *הארץ*, 7(8.5.2017), 2003–2005.
- [2] Bank, A. D. (2021). Technical Assistance Consultant's Report People's Republic of China: Sharing ADB's Operational Knowledge in Technical and Vocational Education and Training in the PRC with CAREC Member Countries Asian Development Bank. December.
- [3] Bank, W. (2020). Comparative and international education. In *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*, 6(11), 951–952.
- [4] Dobbo, T. L. (2018). Higher Vocational Education Reform: Matching Skills to Markets in China. *Int. J. Educ. Stud*, 05(02), 5–7. <http://www.escijournals.net/IJES>
- [5] Haßler, B., & Haseloff, G. (2022). TVET Research in SSA: Recommendations for Thematic Priorities. 7(1), 3–27.
- [6] Jiang, B. (2012). China's TVET: Reform and Opening-up. 1–10. <http://wfc.org/wp-content/uploads/TVET-Reform-and-Opening-up-in-China.pdf>
- [7] Jing, T., Chung, E., & Gregory, M. L. (2022). Vocational Education in China: Its History, Roles, Challenges and the Way Forward. *Journal of Cognitive Sciences and Human Development*, 8(1), 112–121. <https://doi.org/10.33736/jcshd.4497.2022>
- [8] Kinega, M. M. M. (2021). A Comparative Study on Practice of Vocational Education Teacher Training Between Tanzania and China. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Engineering & Multidisciplinary Physical Sciences*, 9(5), 40–53. <https://doi.org/10.37082/ijirms.2021.v09i05.007>
- [9] Kintu, D. (2019). An Exploration of Strategies for Facilitating Graduates' Transition to the World of Work: A Case of Technical, Vocational Education and Training Graduates in Uganda. *International Journal of Vocational Education and Training Research*, 5(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ijvetr.20190501.11>
- [10] Ministry of Education and Sports. (2019). The Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) Policy. July, 1–67. [http://www.eskom.co.za/CustomerCare/TariffsAndCharges/Documents/RSA Distribution Tariff Code Vers 6.pdf](http://www.eskom.co.za/CustomerCare/TariffsAndCharges/Documents/RSA%20Distribution%20Tariff%20Code%20Vers%206.pdf)<http://www.nersa.org.za/>
- [11] Nadialista Kurniawan, R. A. (2021). No 主観的健康感を中心とした在宅高齢者における健康関連指標に関する共分散構造分析Title. *Industry and Higher Education*, 3(1), 1689–1699. <http://journal.unilak.ac.id/index.php/JIEB/article/view/3845><http://dspace.uc.ac.id/handle/123456789/1288>

- [12] Ochola, N., & Kavinda, L. (2019). Grand strategies and performance of private technical and vocational education and training colleges in Nairobi County, Kenya. ... *Academic Journal of Human Resource and ...*, 3(7), 425–440. https://www.iajournals.org/articles/iajhrba_v3_i7_425_440.pdf
- [13] Olema, V. (2018). Contradictions and Complexities to Vocational Education and Training: A case of Uganda. *Peace Engineering Conference*, January, 0–15.
- [14] Pilz, M. (2012). The Future of Vocational Education and Training in a Changing World. *The Future of Vocational Education and Training in a Changing World*, January 2012, 1–592. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-531-18757-0>
- [15] Postiglione, G., & Tang, M. (2019). International experience in TVET-industry cooperation for China's poorest province. *International Journal of Training Research*, 17(sup1), 131–143. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14480220.2019.1629730>
- [16] Reviews, O., & Education, V. (2012). *Education and Training A SKILLS BEYOND*. September.
- [17] Shi, Y., & Bangpan, M. (2022). Young people's participation experiences of technical and vocational education and training interventions in low- and middle-income countries: a systematic review of qualitative evidence. *Empirical Research in Vocational Education and Training*, 14(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40461-022-00136-4>
- [18] Tukundane, C., Minnaert, A., Zeelen, J., & Kanyandago, P. (2015). Building vocational skills for marginalized youth in Uganda: A SWOT analysis of four training programs. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 40, 134–144. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedudev.2014.10.007>
- [19] UN. (2015). *Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls*.
- [20] UNESCO-UNEVOC. (2011). *Initiatives to foster Chinese TVET and TVET Teacher Training*.
- [21] Wang, M. (2006). *Globalization and higher vocational education in China: A case study in Shanghai (Issue September)*.
- [22] Warmerdam, W., & van Dijk, M. P. (2013). China-Uganda and the question of mutual benefits. *South African Journal of International Affairs*, 20(2), 271–295. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10220461.2013.811339>
- [23] Zhang, J., Chen, Z. I., & Wu, Z. (2020). *An Introduction to Technical and Vocational Education in China: Implications for Comparative Research and Practice on Internships*. Center for Research on College-Workforce Transitions (CCWT), September.
- [24] Zouliatou, M. (2017). TVET and Economic Development in Cameroon: Lessons from China. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 8(33), 178-189–189.

Kidega Charles¹,

M. Comparative education, Zhejiang Normal University, China.

College of Education

BAED, Kyambogo University (Economics and Geography)

Email: kidega92@gmail.com

Research interests: Curriculum studies and educational psychology

Prof, Zheng Song²

Zhejiang Normal University, China.

rw60@zjnu.cn

Haufiku Gottlieb Ndambo Djaya³

Zhejiang Normal University, China.

College of Education

cottyfortunecotty@gmail.com

